

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Brye**FIRST NAME:** Laura**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Pr. Cleenewerck**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice 2010, window 8

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **There is section of an essay. Name the section of an essay that should restate the answer to the question, summary the main points and include possible implications and future directions for search?**

 Introduction Body **Conclusion¹** Methodology

2. **Each paragraph in the body of the essay should contain which topics?**

¹ EUCLID, ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1 Essay Writing, *Euclid University*, 2015, 3.

- Topic sentence, supporting sentences, evidence and analysis²**
 - Topic sentence and evidence
 - Introduction, topic sentence, supporting sentences and conclusion
 - Introduction, body and conclusion
3. **Applied questions are common in which fields?**
- Science, biology and business
 - Business, engineering, and medicine³**
 - Healthcare, business and social sciences
 - Engineering, medicine and social sciences**
4. **What is used in bibliographies and reference lists to represent the repeated name of an author or edits?**
- 3-em dash⁴**
 - Parentheses and brackets
 - Commas and dashes
 - Dashes and hyphens
5. **During the development of a doctoral dissertation, a researcher makes knowledge claims. What knowledge claims are they referring to?**
- Post-positivism, advocacy and pragmatism

² EUCLID, 4.

³ Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013, 17.

⁴ Turabian, 93.

- Correlations, causal-comparative and experimental studies
 - Case studies, ethnography, phenomenology, and hermeneutics
 - Ontology, epistemology, axiology and methodology⁵**
6. **The strategy of inquire of qualitative research includes:**
- Case study, grounded theory, ethnography, hermeneutics, narrative inquiry, and/or phenomenology⁶**
 - Descriptive, correlation
 - Causal/comparative, and experimental research
 - Triangulation methods
7. **Which of the following represents the description of sampling in qualitative research?**
- Demographic information.
 - Demographic information, contextual information, perceptual information and theoretical information⁷**
 - Numbers of participants and demographic information
 - Disaggregated demographic information
8. **The literature review provides a clear and balanced description of the current concepts, theories and data relevant to the subject of study. How many years back should the literature review represent the most current work?**
- Ten years

⁵ Bloom & Volpe Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 85-87.

⁶ Bloomberg & Volpe, 10.

⁷ Bloomberg & Volpe, 57.

- Five years⁸**
 - Fifteen years
 - Twenty years
9. **In deciding on an analytical approach to analyzing data, a researcher must consider the differences between analytical approaches.**
- Quasi-statistical approach (converting qualitative data into quantitative data)
 - Template approaches
 - Editing approaches, immersion approaches
 - All the above⁹**
10. **What are the advantages of the WHO house style?**
- House style ensures consistency and increases efficiency of the writing and editing process
 - House style contributes to a corporate image of “one WHO”
 - House style ensures consistency, contributes to a corporate image of “one WHO”, and streamlines and increases the efficiency of the writing and editing process¹⁰**
 - House style provides preferred spelling, punctuation, terminology and formatting.

⁸ Bloomberg & Volpe 2008, 38.

⁹ Bloomberg & Volpe 2008, 99.

¹⁰ WHO, 1.

REFERENCES

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